

Trade Transitions in India's Northeast: Navigating from Barter Systems to Global Value Chains

Rishi Bhargav Das

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce
Gauhati University, Assam

This research paper extensively investigates the shifts in trade within India's Northeastern Region (NER), tracing the journey from traditional barter systems to integration into Global Value Chains (GVCs). The distinctive geography and socio-economic setting of the NER play a significant role in this examination, presenting challenges and opportunities that necessitate thorough analysis. The study delves into historical trade practices, emphasizing the development of barter systems deeply rooted in the cultural and economic identity of the NER. As the global economic landscape undergoes changes, the region encounters the task of safeguarding traditional practices while adjusting to the demands of an increasingly globalized world. Through a combination of empirical research and case studies, the paper aims to uncover specific factors influencing trade transitions in the NER. It explores the roles of infrastructure development, technological advancements, and policy interventions in either facilitating or hindering the region's integration into GVCs. Special attention is given to the unique challenges faced by the NER, such as geographical remoteness and infrastructural constraints, and how these factors shape its involvement in global trade networks. Additionally, the research scrutinizes the impact of trade transitions on various sectors within the NER, taking into account both positive and negative consequences. This study makes a valuable contribution to the broader discussion on global trade transitions by providing a nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities specific to India's Northeast.